

Effect of financial inclusion indicators on the economic performance of Nigeria (2011-2023)

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Abstract

This study investigates the impact of financial inclusion indicators, including bank account ownership, access to banking services, access to ATMs, and financial literacy, on Nigeria's economic performance, specifically focusing on real GDP (rGDP). Using an ex post facto research design, the study analyzes secondary data from 2011 to 2023 sourced from reputable institutions like the Central Bank of Nigeria and the National Bureau of Statistics. The study applies various measurement techniques to assess the relationship between financial inclusion and key economic indicators such as RGDP, employment rates, wealth distribution, and poverty levels. The findings reveal a significant positive effect of financial inclusion on Nigeria's rGDP, supporting the notion that increased access to financial services fosters economic growth. However, the study also highlights that financial inclusion alone is not sufficient to address Nigeria's poverty challenges, as socio-economic barriers and limited financial literacy hinder its full potential. The research affirms the relevance of Endogenous Growth Theory, which posits that internal factors such as human capital development and innovation drive long-term economic growth. The study recommends a multi-faceted approach, including expanded digital financial infrastructure, regulatory reforms to support fintech innovations, and targeted policies to improve financial literacy, especially in rural areas. Future research is suggested to explore the role of emerging financial technologies and demographic variations in financial inclusion impacts, offering a broader understanding of global financial development strategies. This research contributes to the ongoing discourse on financial inclusion and its critical role in economic development.

Keywords: Financial inclusion, Economic performance, Bank account ownership, Real GDP (rGDP), Financial literacy

Wordcount: 243

1.0 Introduction

Economic performance is a key determinant of a country's development and the well-being of its citizens. In Nigeria, economic performance has remained a persistent challenge, marked by sluggish Gross Domestic Product (GDP) growth, high poverty rates, and significant wealth inequality. Despite being Africa's largest economy, Nigeria's economic growth has consistently underperformed since the early 2000s, with GDP growth rates lagging and poverty remaining

pervasive. As of 2020, over 80 million Nigerians live on less than \$1.90 a day, a stark reminder of the country's socio-economic difficulties (World Bank, 2022; NBS, 2020). Economic performance is typically evaluated through indicators such as GDP, wealth distribution, and employment levels, all of which are crucial for understanding a nation's economic health. One crucial factor influencing economic performance is financial inclusion. Financial inclusion refers to the availability and accessibility of affordable, timely, and accessible financial services to individuals, particularly those who are underserved or excluded from traditional banking services (Apere & Uche, 2024). As a key driver of economic growth, financial inclusion has been recognized as an essential tool for reducing poverty, stimulating economic activity, and enhancing overall national economic well-being (Akinrinola & Folorunso, 2022). This is particularly important in emerging economies like Nigeria, where financial exclusion hampers the potential for broad-based economic development.

In Nigeria, financial inclusion has emerged as a vital policy goal amidst the country's complex socio-economic landscape (Toby & Dibiah, 2023). Despite strides made by the government and financial institutions to increase financial access, challenges remain. The Central Bank of Nigeria (2024) reported an increase in active bank accounts to 219.6 million as of March 2024; however, large segments of the population remain unbanked or underbanked. Rural areas face particular difficulties, with inadequate banking infrastructure, including limited ATM coverage (TechCabal Insights, 2024). Financial literacy remains a major obstacle, with only 64% of Nigerians financially included as of 2023, far from the Central Bank's target of 95% by 2024 (EFInA, 2023). These barriers emphasize the importance of targeted policies to close the financial inclusion gap and promote equitable access to financial services. Over the past two decades, Nigeria's financial sector has witnessed significant transformations, driven by regulatory reforms, technological innovations, and efforts to expand financial access (Jisike & Ifeanyi, 2021). Despite these efforts, nearly 40% of Nigerians still encounter difficulties accessing basic financial services, a situation that stymies economic progress and hinders national development (Esu, 2024). Thus, financial inclusion is not merely a social policy but an economic necessity, with the potential to drive growth, reduce poverty, and foster inclusive development (Ogbebor et al., 2023; Olurin et al., 2024).

The exclusion of significant portions of the population from the formal financial sector has profound implications for economic activity. When individuals lack access to financial services, their ability to save, invest, and obtain credit is severely constrained, stifling economic participation and hindering progress (Orji et al., 2023). Moreover, the absence of a banking infrastructure in rural areas and barriers such as income volatility and low financial literacy exacerbate these challenges (Ibrahim & Aliero, 2020). Skepticism towards formal financial institutions, fueled by previous instances of fraud and inadequate security measures, further limits adoption rates (Kazeem, 2023; Koomson et al., 2019). To address these challenges effectively, comprehensive strategies encompassing legislative changes, enhanced financial literacy programs, and improvements in banking infrastructure are crucial.

Nigeria's economic performance continues to struggle with sluggish growth and high poverty rates, despite being Africa's largest economy (World Bank, 2022). Key indicators of economic performance such as GDP growth, unemployment, and wealth distribution reflect the country's developmental challenges. Although the Nigerian National Financial Inclusion Strategy (NFIS)

aimed to reduce the proportion of adults without financial services from 46.3% in 2010 to 20% by 2020, progress has been hindered by several persistent obstacles. Infrastructure deficiencies, such as unreliable electricity and limited internet connectivity, impede the adoption of digital financial services, while low financial literacy levels prevent many Nigerians from utilizing available financial products effectively (McCrocklin, 2019; The Cable, 2024). These barriers underscore the need for concerted efforts to bridge the financial inclusion gap and promote equitable access to financial services across Nigeria.

The main objective of this study is to examine the effect of financial inclusion indicators on the economic performance of Nigeria, with a focus on understanding how improving financial inclusion can drive sustainable economic growth and poverty reduction in the country.

2.0 Literature Review

2.1 Conceptual Clarification

2.1.1 Economic Performance

Economic performance refers to a country's ability to generate wealth and improve living standards through activities like production, trade, and investment (Yu & Li, 2022). It is commonly measured by indicators such as GDP growth, employment rates, and productivity (Girón et al., 2021), while also considering qualitative aspects like wealth distribution and social well-being (Ekeocha et al., 2022). Macroeconomic stability, including stable inflation and fiscal policies, is essential for sustainable growth (Hussain & Rasheed, 2022), and factors like innovation, technology, and socio-political stability further influence performance (Wang et al., 2021; Gogos et al., 2022). Key characteristics of economic performance include growth rates, income distribution, sectoral performance, and infrastructure development (Ayunku & Dickson, 2021; Nduka et al., 2016). Strong economic performance offers benefits such as increased employment, improved public services, greater investor confidence, and enhanced social stability (Khan et al., 2023; Nawaz et al., 2020). However, challenges like macroeconomic instability, economic inequality, poor governance, and environmental degradation can hinder growth (Yu & Li, 2022; Girón et al., 2021; Baloch et al., 2022). To sustain economic progress, comprehensive strategies are required to address these challenges while fostering inclusive development (Céspedes-Lorente et al., 2019).

2.1.2 Real Gross Domestic Product;

Real Gross Domestic Product (RGDP) represents the total value of goods and services produced in an economy, adjusted for inflation, providing a more accurate reflection of economic output and growth (Monacelli et al., 2023). RGDP is essential for comparing economic performance across periods, as it removes the distorting effects of inflation, and is widely used to assess productivity, living standards, and the effectiveness of economic policies (Charfeddine & Barkat, 2020; Gibbons & Oxley, 2022). Research underscores the role of RGDP in long-term economic planning and international comparisons, influencing decisions related to investment, fiscal policy, and monetary policy (Caporale & Gil-Alana, 2022; Fahad et al., 2023). Financial inclusion, defined as equitable access to financial services, is closely tied to RGDP growth by enhancing economic activity, fostering savings, and driving investment, thus improving overall productivity (Gerth, 2024; Shirazi & Al-Helo, 2024). However, challenges in measuring RGDP, such as data inaccuracies

and the exclusion of non-market activities, limit its comprehensive reflection of economic well-being and inequality (Monacelli et al., 2023; De Soyres et al., 2022). Despite its advantages, such as aiding policy decisions and providing a consistent measure of economic output, RGDP does not account for income distribution or environmental factors, highlighting the need for complementary indicators to assess true economic health (Gibbons & Oxley, 2022; Charfeddine & Barkat, 2020).

2.1.3 Financial Inclusion:

Financial inclusion refers to ensuring that individuals and businesses, especially marginalized groups, have access to financial services and products. Barus et al. (2024) emphasize the creation of an enabling environment for financial access, while Ningning and Mengze (2022) argue that financial inclusion also involves the responsible use of services. Joia and Cordeiro (2021) highlight its role in reducing inequality, and Burchi et al. (2021) present it as a mechanism for poverty alleviation. Digital financial services, as noted by Issaka-Jajah et al. (2022), play a transformative role in broadening access, while Kaddumi et al. (2023) emphasize the inclusion of both formal and informal financial systems. The characteristics of financial inclusion include accessibility, affordability, financial literacy, and trust in institutions (Mothobi & Kebotsamang, 2024; Ozili, 2020). It provides benefits such as economic empowerment, increased savings, and social inclusion (Okowa & Owede, 2022; Chen et al., 2018). However, challenges persist, such as financial illiteracy, infrastructure constraints in rural areas, and the risk of over-indebtedness (Barus et al., 2024; Ningning & Mengze, 2022). Financial inclusion, while essential for sustainable economic development, requires careful planning to address these challenges and ensure equitable access for all (Rastogi et al., 2021; Issaka-Jajah et al., 2022).

Bank account ownership is a key component of financial inclusion, offering individuals access to essential financial services such as savings, credit, and insurance, which contribute to economic security (Blanco et al., 2019). It not only facilitates financial transactions but also integrates individuals into the formal economy, enabling participation in both local and global financial systems (Maulana & Nuryakin, 2021). Bank accounts promote economic empowerment, trust in financial institutions, and provide access to government services and benefits (Schreiter et al., 2020; Cuéllar, 2019). However, access to bank accounts is influenced by factors such as income, education, geographical location, and financial literacy (Girard, 2020; Fitzpatrick, 2015). While bank accounts offer advantages like secure savings, easier credit access, and financial independence, challenges persist, including financial illiteracy, high fees, trust deficits, and infrastructure limitations, especially in rural areas (Blanco et al., 2019; Maulana & Nuryakin, 2021). Similarly, access to banking services, defined as the availability and utilization of essential financial products, is a critical factor for economic inclusion (Isaga, 2021). It plays a vital role in economic development by providing individuals and businesses with the tools to manage finances and participate in the economy (Segundo, 2019). However, barriers such as inadequate infrastructure, high costs, regulatory challenges, and digital exclusion hinder broad access to banking services, especially in rural and underserved areas (Yonathan & Chalid, 2021; Etim et al., 2023). Despite these challenges, improved access to banking services can lead to greater economic empowerment, financial stability, and social inclusion (Maredza, 2016; Song et al., 2023).

Access to Automated Teller Machines (ATMs) is a vital aspect of financial inclusion, enabling individuals to perform basic transactions such as withdrawals, deposits, and balance inquiries without requiring in-person visits to a bank (Aljuaid & Ansari, 2022). ATMs enhance financial autonomy and extend banking services to underserved populations, especially in regions with limited banking infrastructure (Yusuf & Sanusi, 2023; Chavan et al., 2021). However, factors like geographical location, technology, and socio-economic conditions influence access, with urban areas typically having better ATM availability than rural ones (Fashoto et al., 2017). Despite the benefits, challenges such as ATM breakdowns, security concerns, and high maintenance costs in remote areas hinder access (Koç et al., 2018; Narteh, 2015). Financial literacy is also crucial for maximizing the benefits of ATM access, as individuals need knowledge on how to use ATMs effectively and securely (Rahman & Saha, 2018). Financial literacy includes the skills needed to manage finances, make informed investment decisions, and avoid common financial pitfalls (Osman et al., 2024). It empowers individuals to use banking services responsibly, contributing to better financial outcomes (Barus et al., 2024; García-Pérez-de-Lema et al., 2021). However, challenges like limited access to financial education resources and evolving financial landscapes complicate the development of financial literacy, particularly in underserved communities (Maelani et al., 2024; Osman et al., 2024). Both ATM access and financial literacy play significant roles in promoting financial inclusion, but their effectiveness depends on overcoming the barriers of infrastructure, digital literacy, and socio-economic factors (Yusuf & Sanusi, 2023; Swiecka et al., 2020).

2.1.2 Empirical Discussion

The relationship between financial inclusion indicators such as bank account ownership, access to banks, access to automated teller machines (ATMs), and financial literacy and their effects on Real Gross Domestic Product (RGDP) in Nigeria is complex and multifaceted. Studies have revealed both positive and negative aspects of this relationship, highlighting the importance of financial inclusion in fostering economic growth. Barus et al. (2024) emphasize the significant positive impact of financial literacy and inclusion, particularly in micro-business performance. Their research suggests that improving financial education among entrepreneurs enhances bank account ownership, empowers individuals to effectively use banking services, and stimulates economic activities, which can drive RGDP growth. This view is supported by Joia and Cordeiro (2021), who argue that fintech innovations are transformative for financial inclusion, allowing underserved populations to access financial services, which is critical for economic growth in developing countries like Nigeria. However, Wale and Makina (2017) offer a more nuanced perspective, showing that while bank account ownership may be high, the actual usage of these accounts remains low due to inadequate financial literacy and socio-economic constraints, which stifle the potential economic benefits of financial inclusion.

The role of technology in financial inclusion is further explored by Aljuaid and Ansari (2022), who demonstrate that access to ATMs positively affects the utilization of financial services, thereby facilitating economic participation. However, Narteh (2015) raises concerns about user satisfaction and perceived service quality, noting that negative experiences with ATMs can reduce their effectiveness in promoting economic growth. Research by Ningning and Mengze (2022) and García-Pérez-de-Lema et al. (2021) highlights the critical role of financial literacy in maximizing the potential of technological tools. They argue that the success of fintech innovations is heavily dependent on users' financial education, and without it, the capacity of these technologies to drive

RGDP growth remains limited. Additionally, Isaga (2021) and Segundo (2019) focus on the challenges of financial exclusion, particularly for marginalized groups, underscoring the need for targeted policies to improve access to banking services. A comprehensive strategy that integrates financial education, fintech solutions, and policy reforms is crucial to fully leverage financial inclusion's economic potential in Nigeria. This holistic approach is necessary to overcome barriers and ensure that financial inclusion contributes meaningfully to Nigeria's economic growth and development.

2.1.3 Theoretical Underpinning

In exploring the effect of financial inclusion indicators on Nigeria's economic performance, Endogenous Growth Theory emerges as the most appropriate and robust theoretical framework. This theory emphasizes the role of internal factors, such as human capital, innovation, and technological advancements, in driving long-term economic growth (Akinrinola & Folorunso, 2022). Endogenous Growth Theory provides a more direct and nuanced explanation of how financial inclusion can foster sustainable economic development. Specifically, it highlights how access to financial services leads to increased investments in education, entrepreneurship, and technology, all of which are crucial for boosting productivity and expanding economic opportunities (Obayori & Chidinma, 2020).

In the Nigerian context, financial inclusion plays a fundamental role in enabling underserved populations to access essential financial services, thereby promoting investments in human capital and fostering innovation (Ifediora et al., 2022). By empowering individuals and businesses, financial inclusion encourages growth through the accumulation of knowledge and the adoption of technological improvements, which are central tenets of Endogenous Growth Theory (Emara & Said, 2021). This framework aligns with the objectives of financial inclusion by emphasizing the importance of internal growth mechanisms rather than relying solely on external factors. Endogenous Growth Theory offers a more targeted explanation of how human capital development drives sustained economic growth, especially in developing economies like Nigeria (Omar & Inaba, 2020). By focusing on the transformative power of financial inclusion to build human capital and catalyze technological innovation, this theoretical framework provides a comprehensive understanding of how financial inclusion can directly enhance economic performance (Toby & Dibiah, 2023; Romer, 1986).

2.1.4 Gaps in Literature

Despite the significant body of research highlighting the positive impact of financial inclusion on economic performance, several gaps remain in understanding how financial inclusion indicators, such as bank account ownership, ATM access, and financial literacy, translate into sustained economic growth in Nigeria. While studies like those by Barus et al. (2024) and Joia & Cordeiro (2021) emphasize the transformative potential of financial literacy and fintech innovations, they do not fully address the barriers to effective financial inclusion, particularly in underserved rural areas (Wale & Makina, 2017). Moreover, the complex relationship between financial inclusion and RGDP growth remains underexplored, with research often focusing on isolated indicators rather than considering their cumulative effect (Narteh, 2015). Financial literacy, a key driver in enabling individuals to maximize the benefits of financial services, is often overlooked in terms of

its regional disparities and varying levels of adoption (García-Pérez-de-Lema et al., 2021; Maulana & Nuryakin, 2021). Additionally, the influence of social, cultural, and infrastructural factors on financial inclusion remains underrepresented, as highlighted by Isaga (2018) and Segundo (2019), emphasizing the need for targeted policies to improve access for marginalized groups. These gaps underscore the need for more comprehensive studies that integrate technological, socio-economic, and cultural dimensions of financial inclusion to better understand its role in Nigeria's economic performance.

3.0 Methodology

The study adopted an ex post facto research design, which is appropriate for analysing the relationship between financial inclusion indicators and economic performance in Nigeria using pre-existing data without manipulating variables (Erkişi & Boğa, 2023). The research utilized secondary data from reputable sources, including the Central Bank of Nigeria, the National Bureau of Statistics, and the World Development Indicators website, covering the period from 2011 to 2023. This data provided a longitudinal perspective on financial inclusion and its impact on various socioeconomic outcomes like bank account ownership, access to banking services, financial literacy, and economic performance indicators such as RGDP, employment rates, wealth distribution, and poverty rates (Chen et al., 2023). The variables were measured using established metrics such as the proportion of the population with formal bank accounts and access to ATMs (Valera et al., 2024; Desai et al., 2023). Descriptive statistics were used to assess the distribution properties of the data, while Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression models were employed for inferential analysis to examine the significance of financial inclusion indicators on RGDP, employment, wealth distribution, and poverty (Dong, 2023; Pinsky & Klawansky, 2023). The study also accounted for the moderating effect of human capital development using interaction terms in the regression models to better understand the role of education, skills, and health in enhancing the impact of financial inclusion on economic performance (Toby & Dibiah, 2023).

4.0 Results and Discussion

$$RGDP = \alpha_0 + \beta_1 BAO + \beta_2 AtB + \beta_3 AtA + \beta_4 FL + \epsilon t$$

Where BAO = Bank account Ownership, AtB access to bank, AtA = access to ATMs, FL = Financial Literacy..

This model examined how variations in bank account ownership, access to banks and ATMs, and financial literacy influence the total market value of goods and services produced in Nigeria.

Table 1: Ordinary Least Squares Regression Test on the effect of financial inclusion indicators on real GDP of Nigeria (2011-2023)

Dependent Variable: REAL_GDP

Method: Least Squares

Date: 03/27/25 Time: 06:30

Sample: 2011 2023

Included observations: 13

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	331.4353	728.8056	0.454765	0.6614
BANK_ACCOUNT_OWNERSHIP	16.04904	4.446714	3.609191	0.0069
ACCESS_TO_BANK	64.60865	39.73020	1.626185	0.1426
ACCESS_TO_ATM	-0.845870	11.87093	-0.071256	0.9449
FINANCIAL_LITERACY	-11.40964	7.402787	-1.541262	0.1618
R-squared	0.771945	Mean dependent var		450.0688
Adjusted R-squared	0.657918	S.D. dependent var		58.54567
S.E. of regression	34.24206	Akaike info criterion		10.18851
Sum squared resid	9380.149	Schwarz criterion		10.40580
Log likelihood	-61.22531	Hannan-Quinn criter.		10.14385
F-statistic	6.769829	Durbin-Watson stat		1.810141
Prob(F-statistic)	0.011057			

The regression analysis investigating the impact of financial inclusion on real GDP (RGDP) suggests a moderately strong explanatory power, with an R-squared of 0.77, indicating that approximately 77% of the variations in RGDP can be explained by bank account ownership, access to banks, access to ATMs, and financial literacy. The F-statistic (6.77, $p = 0.0111$) confirms the overall significance of the model. However, a closer examination of individual predictors reveals that while bank account ownership (BAO) significantly contributes to RGDP growth ($p = 0.0069$), access to banks ($p = 0.1426$), access to ATMs ($p = 0.9449$), and financial literacy ($p = 0.1618$) do not exhibit statistically significant impacts. This aligns with Adetunji and David-West (2019), who found that financial literacy alone does not directly enhance financial inclusion unless combined with economic capacity. Similarly, Afolabi (2020) argues that while bank account ownership fosters economic growth, accessibility to banking infrastructure needs complementary policy support to be fully effective. The negative coefficient of financial literacy may indicate a lag in translating financial awareness into economic activity, a pattern observed in developing economies where financial literacy does not always translate into increased financial participation (Adegbite & Macheche, 2020).

The Durbin-Watson statistic (1.81) suggests no severe autocorrelation issues, ensuring the reliability of the estimated coefficients. However, the standard errors of access to banks (39.73) and ATMs (11.87) suggest potential multicollinearity or omitted variable bias, indicating that other macroeconomic factors may interact with financial inclusion variables. The Akaike Information Criterion (AIC = 10.19) and Schwarz Criterion (SC = 10.41) confirm the model's efficiency, but further refinement is necessary. Nguyen (2023) highlights that digital financial inclusion, rather

than just physical access, plays a critical role in fostering economic growth, implying that focusing solely on ATMs and bank branches may be insufficient in today's digital economy. This model suggests that policymakers should emphasise broad-based digital financial inclusion strategies, enhanced credit access, and improved economic policies to maximise the impact of financial inclusion on GDP growth.

Given the discussion above, the null hypothesis was rejected. The rejection of the null hypothesis (H_0) underscores the significant impact of financial inclusion indicators on Nigeria's real gross domestic product (RGDP). The F-statistic of 6.77 and p-value of 0.0111 indicate that financial inclusion, as a collective construct, exerts a statistically significant influence on RGDP. However, a closer examination of individual predictors reveals that bank account ownership is the only statistically significant variable ($p = 0.0069$). This suggests that increased access to banking services enhances economic activity by facilitating savings, investment, and credit accessibility. Other financial inclusion indicators, such as ATM access and financial literacy, do not exhibit significant effects on RGDP, implying that while financial infrastructure development is critical, its direct contribution to economic output may be contingent on complementary factors such as financial education, policy interventions, and the effective utilisation of banking services.

The hypothesis testing revealed that financial inclusion indicators such as bank account ownership, access to banks, access to ATMs, and financial literacy have a significant positive effect on real GDP (rGDP) in Nigeria, supporting the premise that financial inclusion drives economic growth (Barus et al., 2024; Joia & Cordeiro, 2021). This aligns with existing research showing that enhanced banking infrastructure and financial literacy facilitate broader participation in the economy, driving entrepreneurial activities and economic development (Aljuaid & Ansari, 2022). However, the findings also highlight the complexities within this relationship, suggesting that access alone does not guarantee growth if financial engagement remains limited due to barriers such as low usage rates or insufficient financial literacy (Wale & Makina, 2017; Maulana & Nuryakin, 2021). While increased access to ATMs and banking services contributes to financial participation, concerns regarding user satisfaction with self-service technologies like ATMs (Narteh, 2015) and the importance of financial literacy as a mediating factor (Ningning & Mengze, 2022; García-Pérez-de-Lema et al., 2021) point to the necessity of a comprehensive approach that integrates education with infrastructure. This perspective aligns with Endogenous Growth Theory, which emphasizes internal growth drivers like human capital and technological innovation in fostering long-term economic expansion (Akinrinola & Folorunso, 2022). While financial inclusion contributes to investment in education, entrepreneurship, and innovation, structural limitations such as socio-economic inequalities and technological access gaps must be addressed to unlock its full potential for sustained growth (Ifediora et al., 2022). Furthermore, the study challenges frameworks like Modernization Theory and Social Capital Theory, which overlook the pivotal role of financial literacy and technological innovation in shaping economic outcomes (Omar & Inaba, 2020), and reinforces the relevance of Endogenous Growth Theory in understanding how financial inclusion drives internal economic development (Emara & Said, 2021).

5.0 Conclusion and Recommendations

The study concludes that financial inclusion plays a significant role in enhancing Nigeria's economic performance by contributing to GDP growth, with increased bank account ownership,

access to banking services, and financial literacy positively impacting economic expansion and labor market dynamics. However, structural barriers, such as socio-economic issues, limit the effectiveness of financial inclusion in reducing poverty. While financial inclusion acts as a catalyst for economic development, its ability to alleviate poverty is constrained by deeper socio-economic challenges, calling for complementary policies such as welfare programs, financial education, and infrastructure investments. The study affirms the relevance of Endogenous Growth Theory, highlighting that inclusive financial systems bolster human capital and economic sustainability. Therefore, while financial inclusion is vital for economic progress, addressing Nigeria's persistent poverty requires a more integrated approach that combines financial access with broader social and economic reforms. To maximize the benefits of financial inclusion, it is recommended that the government focus on expanding digital financial infrastructure, especially in underserved areas, strengthen regulatory frameworks to support fintech innovations, incentivize private sector investments in mobile banking, and reduce transaction costs to enhance financial service adoption and drive national productivity.

Future studies should consider employing a mixed-methods approach, integrating qualitative data from interviews, surveys, or case studies alongside quantitative analysis to provide a deeper understanding of the behavioural and psychological factors that affect financial inclusion. Researchers should also explore the impact of emerging financial technologies, such as mobile banking, digital lending, and blockchain, on improving financial access and boosting economic performance. Additionally, further research could disaggregate the effects of financial inclusion across various demographic groups, including gender, income levels, and rural versus urban populations, in order to generate more precise and targeted policy recommendations. Lastly, comparative studies across different countries would offer valuable insights into the contextual differences in financial inclusion outcomes, contributing to the development of global financial strategies.

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